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Bibliometric Analysis of Tour Guiding Research

Abstract

Tour guides are co-creators of tourists' memorable experiences. They are the key players in the tourism industry as they can make or break tourists' experiences. Therefore, interestingly a review was undertaken to surface the topics that have been studied in the research literature, encircling the tour guide profession. This review led to the identification of the themes highlighting various aspects such as problems faced by the tour guides, their competencies, service quality, and training opportunity. The myriad roles of the tour guides have also been reflected in the literature. Evidence of the relationship of the guides with the tourism stakeholders is also salient in the literature. Key findings indicated low remuneration and a non-regulatory framework of the profession are the major problems faced by the tour guides worldwide. Based on the themes identified, future research areas have been discussed with practical and academic implications.

Keywords: *Tour, Tourist, Guide, Competency, Training*

Jel Codes: L83, M31, Z32

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1. Introduction

A tour guide guides tourists in the language of their choice and construes the natural and cultural heritage of a destination (Lovrentjev, 2015). They interpose tourists' experiences and have been regarded as social and cultural mediators in the literature (Ababneh, 2017; Huang et al. 2010; Irimiás et al. 2020; Jahwari et al. 2016; Jahwari et al. 2017; McDonnell, 2001). They are the professionals, who know what is best for tourists and induce positive change in them (Christie and Mason, 2003). Cohen (1985) regarded them as a pathfinder and mentor of

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tourists. They pass on information and knowledge about the tourism destination to their clients.

Tour guides are competent to make or break tourists' experiences based on their knowledge and communication skills (Ap and Wong, 2001; Jahwari et al. 2017). The success of the tourism industry is fundamentally dependent on the tour guides' performances as they are in direct touch with the tourists and they can "make or break their trip" (Zhang and Chow, 2004). They spend most of the time with the tourists (Gelbman and Collins-Kreiner, 2018) and are dutiful for their satisfaction (Geva and Goldman, 1991; Min, 2011); as their performance strikingly determines visitors' satisfaction (Hansen and Mossberg, 2017). A tour leader must endow life to a place, by interpreting it in an intriguing form; making it sensible to the tourists (Mc Grath, 2004). The guides must develop emotional intelligence to pyramid their performances and regulate the different moods of tourists (Min, 2011). Guides have a definite effect on the upgrowth of tourism and the image of a destination based on the service quality provided by them to the tourists (Ababneh, 2017; Huang et al. 2010; Kong et al. 2009; Sandaruwani and Gnanapala, 2016). They foster a link between a destination and tourists (Melia, 2012). They are pivotal for destination sustainability (Pereira and Mykletun, 2012). Guides have to work in concord with different stakeholders of the tourism industry (Gültekin and Icigen, 2019); they must maintain a close relationship with their work partners for better tour guidance (Yen et al. 2018). Their role is becoming challenging to serve the twenty-first-century tourists; being a traditional communicator is not sufficient for the tour guides as they have to choreograph or co-create tourists' experiences for which they have to match their communication competency and skills according to the tourists' expectations (Weiler and Black, 2015).

Despite being a substantial contributor to the tourism industry, guides across the globe are surrounded by various problems such as unfair remuneration (Hu and Wall, 2013), dominance by tour companies (Tsaur and Lin, 2014), seasonality (Ababneh, 2017; Melia, 2012), inadequate training opportunities (Kong et al. 2009), poor working conditions (Sandaruwani and Gnanapala, 2016), low social status (Kong et al. 2009), and physical and social stress (Tsaur and Lin, 2014). Even, guiding fees received by the guides do not match up with their education level and the functional role played by them (Cetin and Yarcın, 2017).

Though, tour guides are assumed as the soul of the tourism industry (Sandaruwani and Gnanapala, 2016); while, they have also been called orphans of the industry (Liljeblad, 2020). Even few of them tagged them as Cinderella of the tourism industry, a profession that is useful and attractive but often neglected (Mak et al. 2011). The profession of tour guides is underdeveloped as Ap and Wong (2001) stated that the profession lacks a defined career path in many countries and their income is dependent on different sources. English-based research literature has a perforation of research studies probing the professional status of tour guides and the problems faced by them (Ap and Wong, 2001; Black and Ham, 2005; Nyahunzvi and Njerekai, 2013 Prakash et al. 2011). Roca (2012) commented that the lack of research studies related to the tour guide profession in the published literature on the English language shows a lack of research interest in the field. Therefore, there is a need for an international research study to gauge the status of the tour guides worldwide; identifying various issues faced by them (Ap and Wong, 2001). The tour guiding profession holds prominence in the academic literature demanding the assessment of the issues of tour guiding and the practical implication associated with it, which are influenced by political economy, socio-cultural identities, and subjectivity (Wise, 2017). Till recent times, the theoretical research on tour guiding is being characterized as weak (Weiler, 2016). Therefore, the purpose of this article is to conceptually review the existing tour guiding research literature and identify the underlying themes, which have been touched upon by the researchers, and open up future research areas in the field of

tour guiding. It would significantly contribute to the development of tour guiding as a profession and the professional development of the tour guides.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Problem Faced by the Tour Guides

The tour guide profession is in despair globally. Researchers from different countries have worked on the issues faced by the tour guides in their country respectively. Chinese researchers are leading on the research front as most of the studies have been carried out from a Chinese perspective. For instance, Kong et al. (2009) reported the deficit of adequate training, experience, and knowledge for the tour guides in China. Further, the guides were underpaid by the travel companies. They had a relatively low profile in terms of education, skills, and attitude plus a low social status. The issues led to the decline in the service quality delivered by the guides causing a rise in the tourists' complaints. Alike, Hu and Wall (2013) observed the problems faced by the tour guides in the Hainan province of China. The issues identified are lenient certification requirements, unfair work relations, unfair remuneration system, lack of monitoring of the guides, lack of effective training mechanism, and absence of protection measures to support the guides. It was found that there is an oversupply of tour guides in the region and the low fair tours were held responsible for the deteriorating quality of tour guiding services. The problem of low fair or zero fair tours is persisting in China over the period of time as Xu and Gehee (2017) also reported that Chinese tour guides are struggling with zero fair tours provided by the tour companies. The guides considered their job challenging after the enforcement of the new law which stops them to force tourists to spend money on shopping or adding extra attractions (Ibid). Sometimes tour guides became scapegoats and tourists turn the blame on them for their dissatisfaction resulting from inferior services received; especially in the case of the below-cost tour (Wang, 2019). Ineffective administration and lack of willingness of government authorities are the reason for this problem (Ibid). A fair remuneration policy is expected by the tour guides in China from the government to deal with this problem (Wang, 2019). Ap and Wong (2001) regarded the itinerary governing by the tour operators as unhealthy industry practices. They opined that tour operators are financially motivated which limits the tour guides' income in Hong Kong. The problems arise because the work of tour guides is seasonal and they work on a freelance basis and had low status.

Not only in China but the tour guiding profession is also surrounded by similar problems in other parts of the world such as India (Aukland, 2016; Prakash et al. 2011), Sri Lanka (Sandaruwani and Gnanapala, 2016) in Asia; Ireland (Melia, 2012), Norway (Roca, 2012) and Spain (Roca, 2012) in Europe; Zimbabwe (Nyahunzvi and Njerekai, 2013) in Africa and other countries such as Jordan (Ababneh, 2017; Mustafa, 2019), Peru (Mc Grath, 2004) and Cuba (Latkova et al. 2018). The findings of the different research studies are alike to the issues faced by the tour guides.

Discussing these issues in Asia, a commission from sales constitutes an important part of the tour guides income in India, as Aukland (2016) presented the case of Rishikesh and Haridwar. Unattractive jobs, the deficit of skill, perceived occupational challenges, job quality, tourism infrastructure, and threats external to the industry are the major challenges faced by the tour guides in India (Prakash et al. 2011). Unfair competition from the unlicensed guide, low social status, low remuneration, job insecurities, and poor working conditions are the problems of tour guides in Sri Lanka (Sandaruwani and Gnanapala, 2016). As Europe is considered, Melia (2012) uncovered the problems of tour guides in Ireland like unsocial working hours, payment issues, and seasonality. Apart, the guides demanded regulation of the profession by the state government. Another study of Europe by Roca (2012), compared the guides' perception of different regions-Catalonia (Spain) and Norway.

The profession is regulated in Catalonia and is not regulated in Norway. Findings suggested that tourist guides' work conditions determine the guide's work behaviour in comparison to their nationality. It was found that the guides in both regions had a low-stress level, higher job satisfaction, and higher intention to remain in the same profession in the future. Though, if compared, the guides in Catalonia were more stressed in contrast to Norwegian guides.

In the African background, lack of job security, little remuneration, meager and expensive training, and fewer career development opportunities are the problems faced by tour guides in Zimbabwe (Nyahunzvi and Njerekai, 2013). Moving to another place on the world map, Ababneh (2017) unveiled three major aspects associated with the profession in Jordan. The first aspect was related to the institutional work environment, which highlights the problems like no provision for minimum remuneration, no medical security provided to the guides on tour, and the absence of any professional association. The second issue explains the problem of seasonality, which is primarily faced by every destination. The third perspective presented the social and physical problems faced by the tour guides such as long working hours, walking long stretches with the tourists, outdoor work, and driving. Tour guides in Jordan consider that the destination lacks proper visitor management and behavioural instructions which help them to monitor the movement of tourists, this paucity hinders them to protect the archaeological sites (Mustafa, 2019). Though, they are committed to regulating positive tourist behaviour protecting the sites particularly cleanliness and picking of archaeological finds (Ibid). Also in Peru, tour guides are not in good condition (Mc Grath, 2004). They need the training to operate in rural areas of Peru.

Capturing the Cuban tour guides' opinion about the development of the Cuban tourism industry, Latkova et al. (2018) indicated that guides believe that the interest of tourists is dependent on varied factors such as culture, nationality, and characteristics. Focusing particularly on to inflow of American tourists to Cuba after "normalization efforts", the guides held a view that it will lead to economic upliftment, exchange of knowledge, and understanding of the political system paving the development of new private businesses. However, there were some problems in way of this ideal situation such as a lack of preparedness for an influx of American tourists, social problems, and a controlled economy. Guide viewed the image of Cuba as a tourism destination in terms of natural beauty, culture, people, history, safe place, and intriguing realities.

A significant work uncovering the numerous hassles faced by the tour guides is by Tsauro and Lin (2014). They identified hassles from three perspectives; hassles in guiding, hassles from tour companies and hassles in personal life. The problems faced by the guides during the guiding process include annoying behaviour of the tourists, irritating tour company employees, different obstacles during the tour, variation in the perception of the guide and the tourists, and being held responsible for the mistake of others. Unmet duties by the tour company staff, inconsistency between the tour features and the guide's style, and unreasonable regulations of the tour company are the problems faced by the guides from the tour companies. At a personal level, the guides face work-family conflict, sometimes they get work-related diseases, had low income, and find it hard to maintain social relationships due to the nature of their job. Interesting research by Aloudat (2017) measured students' perception of the tour guiding as a career choice. Students perceived the profession as interesting which provides freedom and opportunity to gain knowledge and meet new people. However, students were concerned with an unstable income, low social status, and the stressful nature of the job.

2.2 Training of Tour Guides

The previous section of the review establishes the fact that improper training is one of the critical issues of the tour guiding profession. Many authors have brought to the fore the issue

of inadequate training of the tour guides (Kong et al. 2009; Hu and Wall, 2013). Therefore, it increases the curiosity to detect how the problem has been handled in the literature. Hence, this section is providing a critical evaluation of the research studies focused on the training of the tour guides.

A training program must provide a detailed knowledge of the subject, practical guiding skills, and an ability to transform themselves (guides) and the tourists (Christie and Mason, 2003). Training should be grounded in competencies development, knowledge transmission, and skills acquisition (Ibid). Tour guide training is an adult education activity, training should focus on understanding of adults learning, involving appreciation of value differences among individuals, and a method to accommodate the tourists and provide them an opportunity to change their values based on their learning during their trip (Mason and Christie, 2003). Training of tour guides must focus on the physical and communicative perspective of the profession; as training mainly concentrates on interpretative skills (Best and Hindmarsh, 2019).

Training of tour guides should successfully deliver skills and knowledge to improve their capabilities and effectively engage the tourists and enrich their experience (Weiler and Walker, 2014). They have been regarded as experience brokers (Weiler and Walker, 2014; Weiler and Black, 2015). Today's guides need to be highly skilled to meet the need of twenty-first-century tourists and must learn new technology to choreograph memorable tourist experiences (Weiler and Black, 2015). The authors discussed recent trends for tour guiding such as quick availability of information, changing behavioural patterns of tourists, travelers' expectations related to the environment, and social responsibility towards a destination. Guides must adapt communication approaches and skills to meet the tourists' expectations and co-create tourism experiences (Weiler and Black, 2015). Chen and Mo (2013) discussed the computer-aided training for the tourist guide. The components of the training program include story-based animations for 3D tourist sites, multiple practices, and coaching in terms of animated tutorials, self-reflection, collaboration, and articulation of learning technology.

Few researchers have eyed the concept by presenting a case of a particular tourism destination. Professional Certification can improve the tour guides' performance and raise the standards of guiding (Black and Ham, 2005). They presented the case of the Australian Eco-guide program, which rewards the guides who achieve the mentioned competencies and standards. The Australian program was guided by the laid guiding principles. Another study in the Australian context by Carmody (2013) evaluated the potential of SGL's (Savannah Guide Limited) training program for nature-based tour guiding. The program focused on unceasing learning, certifications, mentoring, training, and the development of professional standards. The author suggested the implementation of the model for other nature-based destinations in the world. While Chowdhary and Prakash (2008) have suggested a cafeteria approach for the tour guides' training in India. The cafeteria approach suggests a bifurcation of the training program into small modules, such as short-duration courses. Training should be based on progressive learning, and engagement with localized specialized institutions, and it requires good trainers to train the trainees.

Another study by Lugosi and Bray (2008) has assessed the relationship between organisational culture and tour guides' learning and development. A small tour company in Budapest and its guides were selected for the study purpose. It was ascertained that over a period of time as the guide gets more experienced they strive to continuously improvise their tour scripts, routes, narratives, and stories. It was suggested that more experienced guides can train amateur guides. An organisation focused on guides' development may provide benefits in terms of encouraging learning among the tour guides.

2.3 Roles of Tour Guides

The most cited work concerning the role of tour guides is by Cohen (1985), who classified the guide roles into four distinct sets; instrumental, social, interactionary, and communicative. The instrumental role defines the responsibility of the guide for the smooth conduct of the tour. The social role calls for a guide to act as a leader of the tour group and develop integration among them reducing the tensions. The interactional role depicts the guide acting as a catalyst between the tourists and elements of the destination. While communicative role depends on the formal training received by the tour guides. It is based on the interpretation and fabrication of information. The use of metaphors, similes, proverbs, analogy, and humor by the tour guides during interaction with the tourists depicts a good communication strategy (Dioko et al. 2013). Another classification of guides' roles is provided by Howard (2001) for indigenous tour guides of Australia. Indigenous tour guides have different roles for the tourists such as instrumental leadership role, social leadership role, interactionary mediator role, communicator mediator role, resource management role of motivator, and the role of environmental interpreter. Different researchers have viewed tour guides' roles differently. For example, Hansen and Mossberg (2017) highlighted the guide plus role in tourists' immersion. Guide plus role demands that a guide must focus on individual tourist needs and co-creation of experience, rather than only focusing on service quality. A guide can act as a storyteller, instructor, or social mediator to perform the 'guide plus role'. They argued that a guide can hinder or develop tourist immersion via the co-creation of tourists' experiences. Extending the work of Cohen (1985), Randall and Rollins (2009) added the resource management sphere to Cohen's work to measure the tour guides' performance from tourists' perspectives. The resource management sphere explains the role of a guide as a motivator of responsible behavior and an environmental interpreter. The study was specific to marine tourism especially Kayaking in Canada. It was found that the guides scored well on all the spheres except the role of communicator. The researchers suggested that the training of tour guides must focus on the development of hard skills and soft skills.

Tour guides are indispensable for the preservation and conservation of the natural and cultural heritage of the destination setting out sustainable destination management. A guide should preserve and augment the natural and cultural sites of the destination maintaining good quality guiding (Christie and Mason, 2003). A tour guide must understand the culture of inbound tourists and what problems they face and must have a caring attitude and sincerity in their services (Huang et al. 2010). Jenson (2010) viewed tour guides as social referees between the tourists and the locals and considered their role important for sustainable development. Jenson opined that the welcome of tourists by the locals is largely dependent on social ties between the tour guides and the residents of the host destination. Emphasizing the guide's role as a facilitator of cultural understanding of the host culture among the tourists, McDonnell (2001) ascertained that understanding of culture by tourists led to their satisfaction. Australian tourists were satisfied with their tour because they easily understood the cultural information provided by their tour guide about the special sites, history, geography, and current events of the place (Ibid). Tour guides are linked with the authenticity of tourism destinations; authenticity serves the goals of sustainable tourism (Barre, 2013). Good interpretation by the tour guides is essential for destination sustainability. Poudel and Nyaupane (2013) assessed the effectiveness of interpretative tour guiding for sustainable destination management. They ascertain that effectiveness depends on various behavioral factors of the tourists such as ecological, social, and cultural attitudes. However, interpretative tour guiding was considered important to regulate human behaviour for the sustainability of the host destination.

2.4 Communication Competency of the Tour Guides

The communication competency of the tour guides has been the most widely discussed topic by the researchers. For example, Jahwari et al. (2016) stressed the development of communication competency among the tour guides in Hong Kong. The researchers classified communication competency into verbal and non-verbal competency. Verbal communication is based on the correct usage of grammar for spoken foreign language, choice of correct words, avoidance of slang, and introducing tourists to the locals. While nonverbal competency is based on how the guide approaches the tourists and maintains eye contact with them. In another study, Jahwari et al. (2017) studied that communication competencies including verbal and non-verbal forms significantly influence tour guides' income in terms of tips and general income earned. The research also utilized the big five personality traits theory to determine the guide's income level. Agreeableness, conscientiousness, intellect, and openness were found to be affecting any one of the income sources. While intellect and openness were influenced by the tips earned by the guides in Taiwan. Non-verbal communication (paralanguage and Kinesics) and tour guides' competence (work performance and responsibility) have been reported as a significant predictors of tour guiding service quality in the literature (Jin-Young and See-Won, 2016). Tourists' gaze by the tour guide also acts as a communicative strategy and behaviour of the guides (Gelbman and Collins-Kreiner, 2018). The authors presented five different kinds of tourist gaze; initial gaze, deeper gaze, overall gaze, differentiating and analyzing gaze, and calculating gaze. The gaze helps the guides to evaluate potential economic benefits from the tourists.

It is evident from the above discussion that communication is a key competency of the tour guides, though various other elements style their services. Tour leader services are governed by presentation and communication ability, professional attitude and ability, professional knowledge, and personal integrity possessed by them (Heung, 2008). Key competencies of tour guides include drive, strength, assertion, stress management, management of time, commitment ethics, and change orientation (Min, 2011). The physical attractiveness and sense of humor of a guide significantly determine tourists' attention and guides' explanation efficiency (Tsai et al. 2016). The guides' humor positively led to the formation of tourists' behavioural intentions (Tu et al. 2019).

The performance of the tour guides is dependent on their skills and competencies. In an engaging study, Zhang and Chow (2004) measured Hong Kong's tour guides' performance from Chinese outbound visitors' perspectives. It was found that the tour guides are performing well in terms of professional skills, language ability, and reliability. While they need to focus on their problem-solving abilities. In the Egyptian context, El-Sharkawy (2007) proved that the efficiency of the tour guides is determined by their knowledge and personal skills possessed. Moreover, it was found that Egyptian tour guides pursue an effort to enhance their knowledge and skills and are happy to work as a freelancer. The tour guide's attributes, knowledge, and communication skills provide value-added experiences to the tourists (Seyitoglu, 2020). The guides' competence is a significant indicator of service quality which determines tourist satisfaction and experience (Seyitoglu, 2020).

2.5 Tour Guides' Service Quality

Numerous factors influence the service quality of the tour guide profession. Factors are based on the tour generating country and the host country (Mak et al. 2010). Immaturity of the tourist market and frequent changes in tourist behaviour, unhealthy business practices of travel agents, and their dominance over the market are originating country service quality factors. Intense competition among the tour operators and HR issues with the guides are host destination-specific service quality factors. Similarly, for the Chinese market, Mak et al. (2011) identified six key issues determining the professionalism and service quality

maintained by the tour guides. The layered factors include immaturity of markets, unhealthy business practices adopted by outbound travel agencies, human resources issues, exploitative measures by inbound tour operators, role conflict, and service quality assurance mechanisms. Min (2016) framed the service quality of the tour guides in Taiwan under six dimensions which are reliability, responsiveness, tangibles, assurance, empathy, and culture. The reliability dimension was determined by the factors such as execution ability, ability to handle tourists' emergencies and their complaints, time management, and providing a reliable source to the tourists. Tourists receive various services during their trip such as transportation, guiding, etc. Vélez et al. (2018) developed a model highlighting the significant influence of various tourism services (transportation, food, beverages, tour guides, visits, and activities) on satisfaction leading to the formation of tourists' behavioural intentions.

2.6 Tour Guides and Stakeholders of the Tourism Industry

Tour Guides and Tourists: Tour guides have been regarded as experience brokers in the literature; therefore it is imperative to assess their relationships with the tourists. Huang et al. (2010) conceptualized the relationship between tour guide performance and 'tourist satisfaction with the tour guiding services', 'tour services' and 'satisfaction with overall experience'. It was discovered that tour guide performance has a significant effect on tourists' satisfaction with guiding service which determines tourist satisfaction with the tour services. However, any association of the three variables with tourists' overall satisfaction was not reported. Tour guides' professional competencies in terms of professional skills and attitude help the tourists to develop rapport with the guide, which leads to the tourists' satisfaction with the tour and guides' services and lead to positive word of mouth by the tourists (Hwang and Lee, 2019). The relationships were developed based on the structural model and the study was undertaken in Seoul. Another variable "product knowledge" was influencing the two relationships; first, the relationship between rapport with the guide and word of mouth", and second, satisfaction with guiding service influencing overall tour satisfaction.

Parsons et al. (2019) emphasized the role of tour guides in facilitating tourists' experience of spiritual tourism under five steps process ranging from pre-tour to post-tour. The five steps are "preparation through pre-departure questions, providing enclave to the tourists, mentoring them, reflection and integration of spiritual learning post-tour". Though, not every tourist need to undergo the five stages of their tour experience development. Tourists' behaviour is different from one another and it is based on nationality as perceived by the tour guides in Israel (Pizam and Reichel, 1996). On twenty attributes significant difference was measured among four nationalities (British, American, French, and German), and it was found that tourists of all nationalities are similar in terms of planning their trips and "letter writing". In terms of gastronomy, Caber et al. (2018) found that the guides possess the power to affect tourists' food consumption behaviour. Tour guides are considered important by the tourists in comparison to the tour company (Geva and Goldman, 1991). The authors marked that the satisfaction from the guide lies above the overall satisfaction of the tour and the satisfaction from the tour company (Ibid).

Tour Guides and Tour Operators: Less number of studies have assessed the relationship between tour guides and tour operators; as Lamont et al. (2018) studied the relationship between volunteer tour guides and tour operators. It was found that the tourists in France were dissatisfied with the tour guides because of their poor attitude and poor communication and organisation competency. The authors suggested various human resource development initiatives such as training and focusing on service quality leading to the tourists' satisfaction. While Cetin and Yarcan (2017) measured the difference in perception of the tour operators and the tour guides in Istanbul. A significant difference was found in terms 'group cohesion', 'foreign language', 'holiday experience creation', 'image building', 'itinerary compliance',

‘entertainment’, ‘contract compliance’, ‘identification with tour operators’, and ‘representation skills’. They regarded both parties as important for the development and consumption of the organized tours.

3. Research Method and Findings

A simplified approach has been adopted for this review of literature on the tour guiding research. This review is conceptual, and it has been done to identify future research areas in the field of tour guiding; as the aim of conceptual research is to open up new possibilities for research in the respective field (Xin et al. 2013 cited by Mc Cabe and Qiao, 2020). The article provides a bibliometric analysis of the selected studies on tour guiding research. The bibliometrics approach aims to conceptually assess the evolution and structure of the research concept in the literature (Mc Cabe and Qiao, 2020). Sometimes, authors network the relationships in the literature (Ibid). In this article, bibliometric analysis has been done manually by the author; leading to the identification of different themes in the research literature on tour guiding. The adopted research process is explained in four steps:

Step1-Search Procedure and Screening: The search began with the leading databases including Science Direct, Sage Publications, Emerald Insight, Taylor and Francis Online, Springer, Wiley, and Google Scholar. Prime keywords include “tour guide(s)”, “tour guides and tourism”, “tour guides and destination”. Multiple searches with these keywords were done on all the platforms. Keywords were general to get a comprehensive list of the literature published in the tour guiding research. Keywords were utilized as the screening criteria.

Step2-Selection of Studies: Step 1 yielded 90 documents for the review process. Predefined criteria were used for the selection of the studies. The first criteria mention that the word “tour guide” must be present in the study title. Few exceptions were made to this criteria as few studies (Geva and Goldman, 1991; Jenson, 2010; Mc Grath, 2004; Shephard and Royston-Airey, 2000; Tsaur and Lin, 2014; Velez et al. 2018; Wang, 2019; Yen et al. 2018) were suitable for the review purpose. A synonym for the word “tour guide” had been adopted in the research titles. Such as Heung (2008) and Tsaur and Lin (2014) utilized the word “tour leader” in place of “tour guide”. Another criterion was based on the timeline of the research. Recent studies mostly between 2010-2020 were preferred for the study purpose. To set the research background for this review; a few studies though less in proportion were also selected from the timeline of 2001-10. It helped to understand the past emergence of the problem.

Few seminal works (Cohen 1985; Geva and Goldman, 1991; Pearce, 1984; Pizam and Reichel, 1996; Shephard and Royston-Airey, 2000) of the 20th Century were also taken into consideration. The author was left with 75 documents as 15 of them were excluded on account of duplication, and a few of them were not meeting the first criteria neither they were useful for the present study. Additional three studies were added for suitability of the research. In total, 78 studies constitutes the part of this research.

Step3-Profiling the Studies: After careful selection of the research studies, those were profiled for assessment purposes. Profiling was based on the year, journal, publisher, country, and nature of the study. Figure 1 denotes that a large proportion of studies are recent, which are published after 2010.

Figure 1: Year Wise Distribution of the Research Studies

The top five journals (see table 1) which emerged as the top contributors to the tour guiding research include “Scandinavian Journal of Hospitality and Tourism”, “Tourism Management”, “Current Issues in Tourism”, “Journal of Sustainable Tourism”, and “Annals of Tourism Research”.

Table 1: Journal of the Studies Selected for the Review.

Journal Name	Number of Studies
Anatolia An International Journal of Tourism and Hospitality Research	2
Annals of Tourism Research	4
Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research	2
Current Issues in Tourism	5
EuroCHRIE Conference.	1
Human Relations	1
Indian Journal of Science and Technology	1
Information Development	1
International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management	2
International Journal of Tourism Research	2
Journal of China Tourism Research	2
Journal of Ecotourism	2
Journal of Hospitality and Leisure Marketing	1
Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Research	1
Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management	2
Journal of Human Resources in Hospitality and Tourism	1
Journal of Quality Assurance in Hospitality and Tourism	2
Journal of Sustainable Tourism	5
Journal of Teaching in Travel and Tourism	2
Journal of Tourism and Cultural Change	3
Journal of Travel and Tourism Marketing	1
Journal of Travel Research	3
Journal of Vacation Marketing	2
Master’s Thesis	1
Procedia Economics and Finance	1

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Scandinavian Journal of Hospitality and Tourism	5
The Journal of Tourism Studies	1
The Service Industries Journal	1
Total Quality Management	1
Tourism Management	6
Tourism Management Perspective	1
Tourism Planning and Development	1
Tourism Recreation Research	3
Tourism, Leisure and Global Change	1
Tourismos	2
Tourist Studies	2
Working Paper Series	1

In terms of the publisher (see Table 2) Routledge (Taylor and Francis Group) had an edge over others as 50% (Approx.) of the studies selected for this article were published by Taylor and Francis Group.

Table 2: Publishers Segregation.

Publisher	No. of Studies
Elsevier	14
Emerald	2
Sage	10
Taylor and Francis	37
Wiley	2
Others	10

Table 3 provides an interesting finding that a fewer number of review studies have been done in tour guiding research establishing the need for this article. A large proportion of the studies are based on qualitative and quantitative methods (see Table 3); it depicts that literature is available in the field of tour guiding; however, it needs critical evaluation.

Table 3: Nature of Study.

Nature of Study	No. of Studies	Name of the Studies
Case Study	4	(Ap and Wong, 2001; Black and Ham, 2005; Christie and Mason, 2003; Mason and Christie, 2003)
Descriptive Statistics	7	(Aloudat 2017; Cetin and Yarcan, 2017; Geva and Goldman, 1991; Kong et al. 2009; Loverentjev, 2015; Mc Donnell, 2001; Zhang and Chow, 2004)
Statistical	23	(Alrawadieh et al. 2019; Caber et al. 2018; Chen and Mo, 2013; Chen et al. 2018; El-Sharkawy, 2007; Gültekin and Icigen, 2019; Heung, 2008; Huang et al. 2010; Hwang and Lee, 2019; Jahwari et al. 2016; Jahwari et al. 2017; Jin-Young and See-Won, 2016; Liu et al. 2016; Min, 2011; Mustafa, 2019; Pizam and

		Reichel, 1996; Poudel and Nyaupane, 2013; Prakash et al. 2011; Roca, 2012; Tsai et al. 2016; Tu et al. 2019; Velez et al. 2018; Yetgin and Benligiray, 2019)
Qualitative	26	(Aukland, 2016; Ababneh 2017; Barre, 2013; Best and Hindmarsh, 2019; Chowdhury and Prakash, 2008; Dioko et al. 2013; Gelbman and Collins-Kreiner, 2018; Hansen and Mossberg, 2017; Howard et al. 2001; Irimias et al. 2020; Jenson, 2010; Latkova et al. 2018; Lamont et al. 2018; Lugosi and Bray, 2008; Liljeblad, 2020; Mc Grath, 2004; Mak et al. 2010; Mak et al. 2011; Nyahunzvi and Njerekai, 2013; Parsons et al. 2019; Periera and Mykletun, 2012; Periera and Mykletun, 2017; Seyitoglu, 2020; Tsaur and Lin, 2014; Wang, 2019; Xu and Gehee, 2017)
Literature Review based	6	(Cohen, 1985; Reisinger and Steiner, 2006; Shephard and Royston, 2000; Weiler and Black, 2015; Weiler, 2016; Wise, 2017;)
Mix Methods	9	(Carmody, 2013; Hu and Wall, 2013; Melia, 2012; Min, 2016; Pearce, 1984; Randall and Rollins, 2009; Sandaruwani and Gnanapala, 2016; Weiler and Walker, 2014; Yen et al. 2018)

China and Australia (Weiler, 2016) emerged as the top two countries where the researchers undertook a study on the tour guides (see Table 4).

Table 4: Country-Wise Distribution.

Country	Number of Studies	Country	Number of Studies
Australia	6	Ireland	1
Brazil	1	Israel	3
Budapest	1	Istanbul	2
Canada	2	Jordan	4
China	12	Madagascar	1
Croatia	2	Nepal	1
Cuba	1	Norway	1
Ecuador	1	Peru	1
Egypt	1	Sri Lanka	1
England	2	S. Korea	1
Europe	1	Taiwan	3
France	1	Tonga	1
Hong Kong	3	Turkey	5
India	3	Vietnam	1
Multi Countries	5	Zimbabwe	1

Step4-Review Process and Themes Development: A thorough review was undertaken of the selected 75 studies and key information was extracted for the review purpose. After finishing the review process, the review was scrutinized again for the detection of synonymity of the studies. Based on the similar topic studied, the research studies were classified into different groups in other words thematization was done. The developed themes include “Problems faced by the tour guides”, “Training of Tour Guides”, “Role of Tour Guides”, “Communication Competency of the Tour Guides”, “Tour Guides’ Service Quality”, “Tour Guides and Stakeholders of Tourism Industry”. The themes are discussed in the review section.

4. Conclusion, Implications and Limitations

The tourism industry being experiential in nature demands a higher level of emotional work along with close and dynamic interaction at the touchpoints (Alrawadieh et al. 2020). Tour guides are the frontline workers of the tourism industry who stay in touch with the tourists and spend most of their time with them (Gelbman and Collins-Kreiner, 2018). Therefore, this review article was undertaken to review the tour guiding research. Distinct key themes emerged from the review focused on the aspects of problems associated with the profession, training of the tour guides, their competencies, and service quality provided by them. The role of tour guides is also stressed in the literature along with their relationship with various stakeholders of the tourism industry. Few recommendations based on this review include the development of a fair remuneration system for the guides and regulation of the profession by the respective tourism authorities. The research provides practical implications in terms of the arrangement of adequate training opportunities for the guides and the training programme must focus on the knowledge, skills, and competencies of the tour guides.

Tour guides need to have state of art knowledge as nowadays technology has also become a major threat for them. For instance, many exhibitions held indoors utilizes intelligent guide devices which can be used by the visitors and returned for reuse purpose (Liu et al. 2016). The article also highlighted the need for an educational programme in terms of a vocational degree programme for the profession. It will help the tour guides to gain social recognition. The future research premises evolving from the literature have also been identified, such as research on the identification of a solution to the problems faced by the tour guide in terms of inception and implementation of a fair remuneration system and proper regulatory framework for the profession, which will shape the professional development of the tour guides, attaching some prestige with them.

Professional development of the profession must be followed up, as Shephard and Royston-Airey (2000) commented that the tour manager must periodically review the nature of the divergent roles played by the tour guide. A tour company must review guides' performance from time to time to improve tourists' satisfaction (Jin-Young and See-Won, 2016). Therefore, an annual review of the tour guides' performance is also suggested by the concerned organisations. A cordial relationship should exist between the tour guides and the tourism companies, and the tourism authorities. Tourism organisation needs to cling to motivated and committed tour guides, who have a strong aspiration to deliver great services to the tourists (Jahwari et al. 2017). Governments and tour operators must support the tour leaders (Ap and Wong, 2001).

The literature arrays varied themes, which have been the work area of tourism researchers especially the tour guiding research. The themes that emerged from this bibliometric review include tour guides and the problems faced by them, their competencies, service quality in tour guiding, and the training options available to them. The literature further stressed the wide variety of roles played by the tour guide from cultural ambassadors (Ababneh, 2017) to

the experience broker (Weiler and Walker, 2014; Weiler and Black, 2015), and discussed their relationship with the tour companies and the tourists.

It is well articulated in the literature that the tour guiding profession is surrounded by various problems. Though problems are different, ranging from physical discomfort to social unrest; low remuneration, low social status, and dominance of tour companies. The lack of regulations in the tour guide profession creates chaos as more unqualified guides increase (Melia, 2012). Inappropriate tour guide management lowers the quality of tour guiding services and causes unfair trade practices adopted by the tour guides (Hu and Wall, 2013). A base salary along with some additional benefits must be provided to the tour guides to increase their motivation (Hu and Wall, 2013; Sandaruwani and Gnanapala, 2016; Tsaur and Lin, 2014; Xu and Mc Gehee, 2017). Development of regulation would set the minimum standards for the profession thereby increasing employment opportunities for qualified guides (Melia, 2012). Thus, there is a need to develop a proper legislative framework, remuneration system, and establishment of professional associations for the tour guides profession (Ababneh, 2017).

Sometimes tour guides face emotional exhaustion; travel agencies have a prime role to stop these emotional breakouts by providing a better work environment to the tour guides, paying them at a standard rate, and stopping hiring unlicensed guides ensuring job safety and security (Yetgin and Benligiray, 2019). Destination Marketing Organisations are held liable to inspire a capable person to be a part of the tour guide profession and to achieve that they must address the posed threats and concerns related to the profession (Prakash et al. 2011). It is suggested that tourism practitioners should focus on these problems and take on-ground actions to curb these problems. It is imperative to shift the focus of research from finding problems to finding the solution for these problems.

A lot of expectations are there from the tour guides despite being faced with different hassles in their professional and personal life. Guides must discern the expectations held by travel agencies and the tourists (Salazar 2013, cited by Aukland, 2016) to perform their role effectively. The tour guide's competence is a paramount predictor of tour quality and has immense potential to enormously determine tourists' experience and satisfaction (Seyitoğlu, 2020). Guides must command the quality to transform the tour into an unforgettable experience (Sandaruwani and Gnanapala, 2016). To meet the expectations, the tour guides need quality education and training. Though, inadequate training opportunities are one of the problems circling the profession (Kong et al. 2009).

Therefore, tourism-dependent countries should draw on their resources for the development of tourism employees to stay in the competition (Lovrentjev, 2015). Required knowledge obtained through education programmes is imperative to develop qualified and educated employees such as tour guides (Lovrentjev, 2015). El-Sharkawy (2007) suggested the national theme-based curriculum for the tour guides' training among the academic institutions. The curriculum should be oriented towards experiential learning and skills acquisition at par with the country's assets in terms of attractions (Nyahunzvi and Njerekai, 2013). The concept of sustainability should be imbibed in the curricula (Pereira and Mykletun, 2017). Tour guides provide meaning to what tourists see, therefore they must derive knowledge from multi disciplines especially socio-psychology to understand group dynamics (Reisinger and Steiner, 2006). Future research studies particularly from the socio-psychological field can address the issue of tourist-guide interaction focusing on group dynamics, cognition, and behaviors in social situations (Pearce, 1984).

A large part of the tour guides' training programme is focused on interpretative ability, lacking the focus on the physical and communication perspective of the work (Best and Hindmarsh, 2019). The training programme must be designed keying on the core competencies required for a tour guide work profile. The content of the guide certification

program ought to consider the varied factors such as the roles and types of the tour guides, and the structure and style of the certification programme (Black and Ham, 2005). Tour guides training programme essentially eye on the aspects such as knowledge development about the destination, work ethics and attitude development; interpersonal, organisation, cooperation, and problem-solving skills development (Huang et al. 2010).

Practically, this article is able to highlight the fact that the tour guides are troubled worldwide. Thus, it provides a task to the destination marketers to identify and solve these issues in their countries respectively. The tourism authorities need to pay attention to the development of competencies amongst the tour guides by providing professional training to them. A major loophole is the non-existence of fair remuneration for the profession. Thus, it is a colossal assignment for the authorities to develop and implement a proper remuneration system for the tour guides based on their educational qualifications obtained by them. Tourism organizations; from tour operators to the regulatory body must take care of the tour guides as they are the lynchpin of the tourism industry and should not be left as an orphan of the industry.

The important outcome of this review is that it has highlighted useful academic implications such as the development of training programs and focusing on the content of the training and module designing. The research provides insights to the academia that the guides' training curriculum should be based on national heritage (cultural and natural), competencies, skills, updated knowledge, and sustainability. Further, minimum educational qualifications should be established to enter the profession, regulating the entry of unlicensed guides. The introduction of vocational degree courses in the tour guide profession could lead to the supply of talented and professional manpower for the tourism industry. Additionally, it will attach some respect to the profession raising its social status in society.

Tour guides have an important role in the creation of memorable tour experiences for the tourists. To perform their role effectively they need to sharpen their communication skills and develop their competencies grounded in quality training. Quality services delivered by the guides can create tourists' satisfaction and good experience which will lead to the creation of destination loyalty among the tourists. Loyal customers will return and resulting in recurring economic benefits for the destination. Therefore, the destinations need to appraise the work profile of the tour guides to serve the tourists in the best possible manner.

The review is successfully able to identify distinct research paradigms attracting the research interest of tourism researchers on the topic of tour guiding. The future research avenues have been discussed in the next section.

Despite the abundance of literature in tour guiding research, there are infinite possibilities for tourism researchers to work on tour guiding in the future. The area of utmost importance is associated with the problems of tour guides. Research is needed to work on the problem of low and unregulated remuneration mechanisms specific to a particular country. Conditions are different in every country, therefore no common remuneration system can be made, but efforts can be done specifically for a country. Classification in terms of developed, developing, and underdeveloped economies can also be done to determine tour guides' remuneration. A socio-psychological investigation is also needed to surface the reasons for the low social status of the profession in society. A comparative analysis can also be done of the regulations administering the tour guides in different countries to identify commonalities for the professional development of the guides. Research focusing on the elements of tour guides' training programme is essential for the development of tour guides as professionals in the tourism industry. It is suggested that training programs can be developed based on the nature of a destination such as heritage tourism destination, eco-tourism destination, and so on. Communication competency and problem-solving ability should be incorporated into the training modules as they are the essentials to provide good tour quality. Other areas of

competency such as attitude, behaviour, skills, and knowledge need researchers' attention as literature has mainly focused on communication competency. Competencies of a tour guide are the pre-requisites to offer a good quality tour which led to the tourists' satisfaction. An empirical study is needed, oriented toward the identification of service quality measured by tour guides, which can be generalized.

Further, research can enquire into the working relationship of the tour guides with the tourism organisations like tour companies, tour operators, travel agencies, government authorities, and regulatory bodies. It can be assessed how these organisations foster motivation in tour guides' life and how they help them to perform their roles effectively. For example, if a base salary system is introduced for a particular destination, it will reduce the economic burden of the guide and motivate them to perform better. The work-life balance of the tour guides also needs due consideration. Their job is tedious and demanding, therefore it is necessary to study how tour guides are maintaining their work-life balance? Are they able to balance? If not, why? If yes, how they are doing that? Answers to these questions would be beneficial for tourism professionals (guides) across the world.

This article is a bibliometric analysis of the selected research studies. It suffers from various limitations. First, the article does not provide any empirical support for the findings. Second, there may be a chance of bias in the selection of studies for this review. Though proper care was taken. Third, it is not specific to any country, it is discussing the tour guide environment in a general sense based on the previous literature. Fourth, the review is done manually without any technical assistance, thus a chance of human error could arise.

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